

INFLUENCE OF CUSTOMER LOYALTY PROGRAMS ON REPEAT PURCHASE BEHAVIOR: A STUDY ON THE PERSPECTIVE OF MILLENNIALS

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the influence of customer loyalty programs on repeat purchase behavior of Millennials. It highlighted that the effect of current types of customer loyalty programs on repeat purchase behavior remains unclear. Thus, this study aimed to assess the effectiveness of selected customer loyalty programs, to know how Millennials achieve repeat purchase behavior, and to determine the relationship between customer loyalty programs and repeat purchase behavior. A quantitative approach using purposive sampling was employed, involving 407 Millennial respondents from Manila, Philippines. Data were analyzed using weighted mean and Pearson correlation. The researchers determined a strong positive relationship between customer loyalty programs and repeat purchase behavior. Millennials were found to be cost-sensitive, favoring programs that offer immediate rewards with little to no cost. Furthermore, it was found that Millennials prioritize customer satisfaction when assessing their repeat purchase behavior. The results confirm that businesses can achieve sustainable growth by implementing well-designed loyalty programs that reflect Millennial preferences. The findings imply businesses to continuously refine these programs to ensure they align with evolving customer desires, ensuring long-term customer retention and engagement. While this study offers valuable insights, its scope is limited to Millennial respondents in Manila, concentrates solely on online loyalty programs, and relies exclusively on quantitative methods. Future studies should explore generational differences and other influencing factors for broader insights.

Keywords: *Brand Loyalty, Customer Loyalty Programs, Customer Satisfaction, Purchase Discount, Repeat Purchase Behavior*

INTRODUCTION

Marketing in business is a continuous process of innovation that guides companies in providing benefits and values in their products and services for their customers, partners, and society. A marketing approach defines what the company will be focusing on or prioritizing when marketing its products and services. One of the contemporary marketing approaches is relationship marketing, where companies focus on maintaining a strong relationship with their current customers. As society continues to evolve, trends rapidly change and increase, requiring companies to act fast and think fast. One common relationship marketing strategy is implementing customer loyalty programs, a series of strategies and activities developed by a company to reward and incentivize customers to continue purchasing and using its products or services. Repeat purchase behavior refers to the way consumers assess whether or not they will be repurchasing a product or service they have already bought. Having a high percentage of customers who repeat purchases may define how well a company is doing in terms of marketing as well as enhance brand reputation.

There is an increasing concern over the effectiveness of customer loyalty programs in driving repeat purchase behaviors among Millennials. The usage of loyalty programs among Millennials is declining at a rate of 2-3% per year despite the increase in loyalty programs (Bowen & McCain, n.d). Despite the high spending potential of Millennials, they are often characterized by low brand loyalty, which presents significant challenges for businesses to engage Millennials and retain them through loyalty programs as well as encourage their repeat purchases. While some studies have examined customer loyalty programs and their general effects, there are limited studies on how specific types of customer loyalty programs influence repeat purchase behavior among Millennials. The researchers found an empirical research gap where there are only few studies that examine the influence of customer loyalty programs on repeat purchase behavior in the Philippines. By identifying which loyalty program is most effective for engaging Millennials, this study aims to provide businesses with actionable recommendations to improve their loyalty programs and enhance customer retention. Customer loyalty programs may be effective in increasing revenue and customer retention, thus building stronger customer relationships with customers. This study aims to solve the existing problem of whether implementing customer loyalty programs has a significant influence on repeat purchase behaviors or not.

Review of Related Literature

Customer Loyalty Programs

Customer loyalty programs are strategies designed to foster and maintain strong relationships with customers. These programs help in increasing brand loyalty and fostering repeat purchases as they offer incentives and rewards to consumers (Bade et al., 2024).

Reward Points. A type of reward earned through reward promotions or shopping in designated categories. Gabel and Guhl (2021) studied the loyalty program of a German supermarket chain and found that reward points can significantly increase repeat purchases, while personalized coupons are more effective in promoting the use of self-service checkout terminals.

A points program enables customers to earn points whenever they make a purchase and redeem gifts and discounts from the points accumulated (Iqbal et al., 2023). They concluded that implementing a points program will encourage customers to shop regularly.

Purchase Discounts. Discounts can make promotions more attractive which potentially leads to an increase in customer engagement and customer loyalty. However, over-reliance on discounts can sometimes lead to customers expecting lower prices consistently, which might affect long-term loyalty if not managed carefully, that means that brands need to know how to balance discount strategies (Zhou & Jung, 2023).

Direct discounts and bundled sales do not have a significant impact on consumer purchasing decisions as they may make customers feel forced to buy unnecessary items (Ren et al., 2022). Merchants should give priority to quantity discounts and coupon discounts when formulating promotional strategies, which can not only promote sales growth, but also help build customer loyalty and encourage repeat purchases.

Additional Gifts or “Freebies”. Bharadwaj and Bezborah (2021) studied the relationship between non-monetary promotions and brand loyalty. The study found that gift promotions can significantly increase brand loyalty, while also having a positive impact on perceived quality and customer-perceived value.

Lubensky and Schmidbauer (2020) studied the impact of pre-sale trials (sample products) on consumer behavior. The study emphasizes that when companies provide free trials, they need to consider various factors such as product quality and matching value, because consumers not only pay attention to the quality of the trial product, but also pay more attention to how it meets personal needs.

Subscription Programs. Subscription plans are popular among retailers and marketplace platforms, where members can pay upfront to enjoy exclusive benefits. Subscriptions significantly increased customer purchases, with one-third of the increase coming from economic benefits and the rest attributable to the sunk cost fallacy (Iyengar et al., 2022).

Subscriptions are particularly effective at activating low-engagement users than for highly engaged users (Wu et al., 2024). The results show that subscription programs have a significant effect on improving and driving user engagement.

Tiered Loyalty Programs. Tiered loyalty programs are designed to offer increasing benefits as customers move up the tiers. Exclusive benefits that gradually

increase with the membership level can create value perception and increase repeat purchase rates (Kaur, 2024). In particular, personalized rewards and tiered benefits programs can effectively improve customer retention.

Qi et al. (2022) studied the strategic significance of product line development in meeting the diverse needs of consumers. When companies combine value-added services with tiered loyalty programs, they can enhance customer retention and increase sales. The results show that value-added services in tiered loyalty programs can enhance customer loyalty and increase purchase rates as this enhances customer loyalty and encourages customers to purchase more.

Repeat Purchase Behavior

Almursyid et al. (2024) indicated factors such as customer satisfaction, product quality, affordability, comfort, trends and environmental influence, and brand image that significantly influence repeat purchases. Additionally, the results suggest that brand loyalty and perceived value play crucial roles in the repeat purchase behavior of consumers.

Service Quality. Price and service quality has an effect on consumer behavior in determining repeat purchase intentions with shipping cost as an intervening factor. When consumers receive good-quality services and appropriate shipping costs, they are happy and willing to purchase again from the shop (Panjaitan & Butar-Butar, 2023).

Aninda and Roosdhani (2024) found that although service quality does not have a direct impact on repurchase intention, it has a positive impact on customer satisfaction and trust, thereby leading to a significant increase in repurchase intention. The study shows that customer satisfaction and trust in service are important in determining repurchase.

Brand Loyalty. Chauhan (2023) studied the role and impact of brand loyalty on repeat purchase behavior in the field of fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG). It was found that brand reputation, product quality, price and promotional activities play an important role in shaping consumer brand loyalty, and brand loyalty can encourage consumer repeat purchase behavior.

Saputra et al. (2024) studied the impact of brand image, brand personality and brand trust on brand loyalty, and used quantitative research methods to collect data from 100 respondents. The results show that these three factors together have a positive and significant impact on brand loyalty, emphasizing that maintaining these factors is important for building brand loyalty and enhancing customer loyalty.

Product Quality. Sainy and Joshi (2024) studied the impact of product quality on customer satisfaction, loyalty, and repeat purchase behavior. They found that high product quality can significantly improve customer satisfaction, which builds loyalty by meeting expectations and making customers feel that they are getting value for money,

thereby promoting repeat purchases and helping companies maintain customer relationships.

Tutor et al. (2024) explored the relationship between product quality dimensions and brand loyalty in the cosmetics industry. They concluded that the two variables were positively correlated, emphasizing that product quality and brand loyalty are crucial to formulating effective marketing strategies.

Customer Satisfaction. Afinia (2024) found that there is a significant and positive relationship between customer satisfaction and repurchase intention in the e-commerce context. The study concluded that prioritizing customer satisfaction is important in enhancing customer loyalty which could then result in repeat purchases from the customer.

Customer experience directly influences customer satisfaction, as a positive experience can lead to a higher satisfaction level, enhancing customer loyalty and brand value (Tu et al., 2024).

Brand Recall and Recognition. Kato (2021) studied the relationship between brand concept recall and repeat purchase intention. Based on data from multiple Japanese brands and users, he found that except for Facebook, brand recall helps promote repeat purchases. Therefore, it is important for companies to evaluate consumers' loyalty due to recalling brand concepts to enhance brand loyalty.

Lee (2024) explored brand recognition and analyzed the difference between brand recognition and brand recall. Research shows that brand recognition is a key element of marketing strategy. The unique design elements of a brand help consumers quickly identify the brand, which helps the brand achieve differentiation and cultivate loyalty.

Influence of Customer Loyalty Programs on Repeat Purchase Behavior

Chandrasekhar et al. (2024) conducted a study on the relationship between impulse buying and loyalty programs. The researchers highlighted that the relationship between customer loyalty programs and repeat purchase behavior is significant and multifaceted. The study identified that impulse purchases are driven by emotional and psychological factors, which includes expectations of rewards and excitement in earning points. The anticipation of rewards and other psychological factors drive repeat purchase behavior, making it crucial for businesses to stimulate customer interest and loyalty.

The study conducted by Kaur (2024) focused on examining the impact of loyalty programs on customer retention within the retail industry. Kaur (2024) hypothesized that customer retention is improved when loyalty programs are well-designed, which leads to increased satisfaction and encourages repeat purchases. It highlights the role of psychological factors and emotional connections that affect the perception of consumers on customer loyalty programs, which also affects their repeat purchase behavior.

Research Questions

As competition increases, companies use customer loyalty programs to retain existing customers and attract new ones. These programs are designed to strengthen relationships and encourage repeat purchases, but the specific impact of specific programs on repeat purchases remains unclear. This study focuses on Millennials, who are more likely to engage with loyalty programs, and investigates how specific programs influence their repeat purchase behavior. By exploring this, the study aims to provide companies with insights to improve their loyalty programs.

Specifically, this research aims to answer the following specific questions:

1. How do Millennials assess the effectiveness of customer loyalty programs in terms of:
 - a. Reward Points
 - b. Purchase Discounts
 - c. Additional Gifts or “Freebies”
 - d. Subscription Programs
 - e. Tiered Loyalty Programs
2. How do millennials achieve repeat purchase behavior based on the following:
 - a. Service Quality
 - b. Brand Loyalty
 - c. Product Quality
 - d. Customer Satisfaction
 - e. Brand Recall and Recognition
3. What is the relationship between customer loyalty programs and the repeat purchase behaviors of Millennials?
4. What can be improved in the customer loyalty programs to encourage Millennials to repurchase a product or service?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

This study was conducted in the City of Manila, Philippines. This area was chosen for the study mainly because of its convenient location, making it easier for the researchers to conduct the study, as well as the ease of data collection, which allows for relatively easy access to the study data. With the large population of Manila, it can represent a significant amount of Millennials in the Philippines. Additionally, there is a large and diverse business sector in Manila, making it suitable for researchers to gather information from residents as they are more exposed to different marketing strategies. This area allows for valuable insights that lead to a generalizable conclusion that helps optimize the customer loyalty programs of companies in order to attract more Millennial consumers.

Research Design

This study employs a quantitative correlational approach to examine the relationship between different customer loyalty programs and Millennials' repeat purchase behavior. This approach is ideal as it enables the researchers to collect numerical data that can be analyzed statistically to identify patterns and relationships. The nature of a quantitative correlational approach guides the researchers in the process of collecting and analyzing the data gathered. This also reminds the researchers that manipulating the variables is not needed and should not be done in a correlational study. The correlational method helps the researchers understand how the variables influence each other and the nature of their relationship. A correlational approach is best for a study that seeks to identify and analyze the strength and direction of relationships between variables (Panjaitan & Butar-Butar, 2023).

This study used purposive sampling, a non-probability sampling technique where the researchers select samples based on a specific criteria. The population was based on the 2020 Household Population by Age Group, Sex, Province, and City/Municipality report from the Philippine Statistics Authority, focusing on individuals aged 25 to 39, totaling 464,739 people. This age range was selected as they would be part of the Millennial age group in the year 2024. Using the Raosoft application, the sample size was calculated to be 384 participants with a 5% margin of error at a 95% confidence level. The respondents were selected based on these criteria: (1) should be a Millennial in the year 2024, (2) should be engaging with at least one customer loyalty program, and (3) should be a customer that purchases monthly in the online platforms like Shopee, Lazada, Shein, Starbucks App, Grab, and FoodPanda. Through purposive sampling, the study can gather more relevant and insightful data by selecting participants who are directly involved with the loyalty programs (Salleh et al., 2020). Lawrence and Muathe (2022) stated that using purposive sampling in their study was an efficient way to gather data from a manageable number of respondents who were most likely to provide relevant information.

Research Participants

Millennials were chosen as the participants for this study due to their significant exposure to and engagement with customer loyalty programs. Understanding Millennials' perception towards customer loyalty and how they achieve repeat purchases can guide businesses in tailoring their programs to be more appealing, fostering long-term relationships with customers in this demographic. At this age group, they do not make impulsive decisions as they tend to analyze and seek relevant information before making purchases, ensuring more thoughtful and deliberate choices. As stated in a study conducted by Whalen et al. (2023), Millennials represent a significant portion of the market, making it crucial to understand their consumer behavior and loyalty patterns. Additionally, Millennials represent a demographic that is experiencing a shift in consumer behavior, from frequent brand switching to a more loyalty-centered approach, where their insights can serve as a foundation for future research that explores brand loyalty among different generational cohorts (Opati et al., 2023).

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers began by consulting their research adviser to review and provide feedback on the initial version of the questionnaire. The suggestions were incorporated to improve the questionnaire's clarity, structure, and alignment with the study's objectives. Afterward, the revised questionnaire was validated by three authorities who hold master's degrees, although their fields of expertise were not directly related to business. Once the questionnaire was finalized, it was distributed online via Google Forms to 34 Millennials living in Manila for a pilot testing. The researchers used purposive sampling to reach respondents, sharing the link through various social media platforms and communication channels. After the researchers were able to successfully gather 407 responses, they were carefully tabulated and checked for accuracy before being submitted to a statistician for analysis. The results from the statistical treatment were then reviewed and interpreted by the researchers to understand how customer loyalty programs influence Millennials' repeat purchasing behavior.

Data Analysis

The data was analyzed through computing the weighted mean and using the Pearson Correlation coefficient. Weighted Mean was used to get the average level on how Millennials assess the effectiveness of customer loyalty programs and how Millennials achieve repeat purchase behavior. By getting the weighted mean, the researchers are able to evaluate the variables by the given factors more accurately. Moreover, the weighted mean was verbally interpreted through the use of a four point Likert scale. The four point Likert scale is interpreted as follows: Responses with a mean score ranging from 3.25 to 4.00 indicate that respondents strongly agree with the statement. A mean score within the range of 2.50 to 3.24 reflects an agreement with the statement. Scores falling between 1.75 and 2.49 suggest disagreement, while mean scores from 1.00 to 1.74 represent strong disagreement. This interpretation helps in understanding the level of respondents' agreement or disagreement with the survey items.

Additionally, Pearson Correlation coefficient was used to determine the relationship between customer loyalty programs and the repeat purchase behaviors of Millennials. This analysis method helped the researchers measure the strength of the relationship between customer loyalty programs and repeat purchase behavior. Correlation is an effect size that can verbally describe the strength of the correlation by using the interpretation table. A correlation coefficient ranging from .90 to 1.00 or -.90 to -1.00 indicates a very high positive or negative correlation, showing a strong linear relationship. Values from .70 to .90 or -.70 to -.90 reflect a high positive or negative correlation, suggesting a strong association between variables. A coefficient within .50 to .70 or -.50 to -.70 signifies a moderate positive or negative correlation, while values from .30 to .50 or -.30 to -.50 indicate a low positive or negative correlation. Finally, coefficients ranging from .00 to .30 or -.00 to -.30 suggest a negligible correlation, implying little to no linear relationship between the variables.

RESULTS

Table 1
Millennials Assessment of the Effectiveness of Customer Loyalty Programs

Particulars	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Reward Points	3.17	0.97	Agree
Purchase Discounts	3.10	0.97	Agree
Additional Gifts or “Freebies”	3.16	0.90	Agree
Subscription Programs	3.03	0.93	Agree
Tiered Loyalty Programs	3.01	0.94	Agree
OVERALL	3.10	0.89	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.74 Strongly Disagree, 1.75-2.49 Disagree, 2.50-3.24 Agree, 3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 2
Factors Affecting Millennials in Achieving Repeat Purchase Behavior

Factors	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Service Quality	3.20	0.96	Agree
Brand Loyalty	3.16	0.93	Agree
Product Quality	3.21	0.93	Agree
Customer Satisfaction	3.22	0.95	Agree
Brand Recall and Recognition	3.18	0.96	Agree
OVERALL	3.20	0.91	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.74 Strongly Disagree, 1.75-2.49 Disagree, 2.50-3.24 Agree, 3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 3
Relationship Between the Customer Loyalty Programs and the Repeat Purchase Behaviors of Millennials

Correlation between	r-value	Description	p-value	Remark
Customer loyalty programs and the repeat purchase behaviors of Millennials	0.92	Very High	.000	Significant

Note: If p-value is <0.05 the level of significance is statistically significant, while if p-value is >0.05 the level of significance is not statistically significant.

DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the assessment of Millennials on the effectiveness of customer loyalty programs. The table suggests that Millennials prefer the Reward Points program and Additional Gifts or “Freebies” as both programs offer immediate rewards, fulfilling their desire for quick outcomes from their actions. This is supported by the study of Gabel

and Guhl (2021) stating that reward points have a strong impact on consumers' repeat purchase behavior due to points-pressure effect. This means that consumers are motivated to put more effort in collecting points as they near rewards. Similarly, Iqbal et al. (2023) discovered that points programs increase buying interest and customer loyalty because points can be redeemed for rewards in the future. Additional gifts or "freebies" have a positive impact on the repeat purchase intentions of consumers; however, freebies that are low quality or are not aligned with consumer preferences may result in a negative impact (Bharadwaj & Bezborah, 2021; Stäbler, 2021). Millennials are price-sensitive consumers who favor affordable products to save money, which show that Millennials are strongly motivated to buy discounted products, particularly during holidays or when discounts are about to expire. While purchase discounts still have an influence on Millennials' repeat purchase behavior as it makes products more affordable and accessible, discounts become less interesting due to its timely nature. Discount strategies offer immediate benefits which not only increase sales but also boost customer engagement, foster loyalty, and encourage repeat purchases, with holiday discounts being particularly effective due to their sense of urgency and exclusivity (Ren et al., 2022; Zhou & Jung, 2023). Although subscription programs and tiered loyalty programs got the lowest mean score, that still has an influence on Millennials' repeat purchase behavior, suggesting that Millennial consumers rather receive additional benefits with no additional cost than enjoying exclusive benefits that require spending more money. However, despite a lower preference for subscription and tiered loyalty programs, these programs still drive repeat purchases by offering long-term benefits and unique experiences. Subscription programs have a significant impact on improving and driving user engagement while perceived value of paid membership influences the user's intentions to continue using these services (Park, 2024; Wu et al., 2024). This is further supported by Kaur (2024) and Qi et al. (2022), who argue that tiered loyalty programs create a sense of value and exclusivity.

Table 2 presents the analysis of the factors that affect Millennials in achieving repeat purchase behavior. The table suggests that Millennials prioritize satisfaction with their purchase experience when deciding whether to repeat purchases from a brand. This highlights the importance of providing a good overall customer experience, delivering high-quality products and exceptional customer service to foster loyalty among Millennial consumers. Customer satisfaction is key to their repeat purchase behavior, as they value the entire purchasing process and how it shapes their attitude toward a brand. A positive customer experience boosts satisfaction, fostering loyalty and increasing brand value (Tu et al., 2024). Additionally, Tian and Sakurai (2023) and Afinia (2024) found that improving perceived value and prioritizing customer satisfaction are essential for enhancing loyalty and encouraging repeat purchases. Moreover, high quality products and good customer service leads to a satisfied customer which may result in a repeat purchase behavior. This claim is supported by Sainy and Joshi (2024), who stated that high product quality makes customers feel that their purchase is worthwhile, thereby building customer loyalty. When both product and service quality are considered together, they have a positive and significant impact on customer satisfaction (Tussifah and Navitsha, 2021). This also aligns with the study results of Panjaitan and Butar-Butar (2023), which show that consumers are more likely to make repeat purchases from the same brand when they

receive high-quality services. While the level of familiarity and loyalty with a brand affects the repeat purchase behavior of Millennials, they are not equally prioritized as customer satisfaction, product quality, and service quality. Surprisingly, this reveals that when Millennials exercise repeat purchase behavior, they do not heavily rely on their loyalty to a brand. Brand loyalty is less influential because consumers can easily switch to brands that meet their needs and offer better products. Nevertheless, both brand recall and recognition and brand loyalty are still factors that motivate repeat purchases. Chauhan (2023) emphasizes the importance of brand loyalty in maintaining customer relationships and achieving sustainable growth in a highly competitive market and concludes that brand loyalty contributes to the increase of repeat purchase behavior among consumers. Additionally, Kato (2021) and Lee (2024) found that brand recall plays a role in customers' repeat purchase intentions, while brand recognition is a key element of a marketing strategy.

Table 3 presents the relationship between customer loyalty programs and repeat purchase behavior of Millennials. The computed correlation coefficient ($r = 0.92$) indicates that there is a strong positive correlation between the variables, suggesting that customer loyalty programs influence repeat purchase behavior. This means that as customer loyalty programs increase, repeat purchase behavior also increases. This high correlation can be interpreted as customer loyalty programs automatically influence repeat purchase behavior. This is consistent with the findings of Chandrasekhar et al. (2024) who stated that loyalty programs encourage repeat purchases and concluded that a significant relationship is present between the variables. Likewise, Kaur (2024) stated in his study that customer loyalty programs are closely related to repeat purchase behavior, as they create incentives and emotional connections that encourage customers to return and engage with the brand more frequently.

Conclusions

The researchers found that reward points and additional gifts or “freebies” are the most effective customer loyalty programs. This result reflects how Millennial consumers value receiving immediate rewards while also maximizing the value of their money. Purchase discounts are almost as effective as the above mentioned, as Millennials are price-conscious consumers who seek for more affordable alternatives that give the same benefit as high-priced products. Lastly, subscription programs and tiered loyalty programs are not as effective as the first three loyalty programs, but they still have a significant influence on Millennials' purchases. Both subscription programs and tiered loyalty programs provide long term benefits and unique experiences which encourages Millennial consumers to stay loyal. Overall, reward points, freebies, purchase discounts, subscription programs, and tiered loyalty programs are effective in carrying out its main objectives.

Millennials achieve repeat purchase behavior mainly because of customer satisfaction, product quality, and service quality. They are attracted to businesses that provide them a positive overall experience that reaches their expectations. Furthermore, product quality and service quality are key priorities for Millennials, as they prefer not to

waste money. They seek affordable, high-quality products that provide satisfaction and value. Brand loyalty and brand recall and recognition are not as prioritized as the first three factors, but still play a crucial role in achieving repeat purchase behavior. Millennials may remember a brand, but the actual decision to repurchase is more strongly influenced by how well the product or service meets their needs in terms of quality and satisfaction.

There is a high positive correlation between customer loyalty programs and repeat purchase behavior. This suggests that implementing customer loyalty programs is essential as these programs significantly influence Millennial consumers' repeat purchase behavior. The high positive relationship of the variables indicate that customer loyalty programs automatically result in repeat purchases.

To attract and retain Millennial consumers, businesses should prioritize customer loyalty programs that offer immediate rewards—particularly reward points and freebies—since Millennials value quick returns and maximizing value for money. While these are the most influential, purchase discounts also play a key role in boosting satisfaction and encouraging word-of-mouth marketing, especially when timed around peak shopping periods. To foster long-term loyalty, businesses should offer useful, personalized rewards and ensure a high-quality customer experience throughout the purchasing process. Regularly collecting feedback and delivering consistent product and service quality are essential for maintaining satisfaction and loyalty. Although brand recall and loyalty are less influential in Millennials' repeat purchases, businesses should still maintain strong brand visibility and a positive reputation through marketing and social media. Loyalty programs should feel worthwhile, offering flexible, affordable, and exclusive benefits to match Millennials' preferences and expectations.

Recommendations

Based on the study's results, several suggestions and recommendations are made for enhancing customer loyalty programs and for future researchers to further dive into this topic. Future research should compare the differences in preferences of different generations of consumers for loyalty programs, expand the research to other geographical locations to examine the impact of location factors on program effectiveness, and compare the impact of online and offline on loyalty programs. At the same time, study the impact of consumer economic status and technological literacy on participation, and use a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods to study consumers in depth. At the same time, the research can also explore the weak links in the loyalty program of this study and explore the mediating factors between loyalty programs and repeat purchase behavior. Companies can combine tangible incentives such as point rewards and additional gifts with service quality, and consider other factors such as after-sales service and holiday discounts to improve customer loyalty and customer retention.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers ensured that the study was conducted in full adherence to ethical standards. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and it was clearly stated

in the survey that participation was entirely voluntary, with the option to withdraw at any time without consequence. Respondents were assured that all information provided would remain confidential and would be used solely for the purposes of the study. Anonymity was maintained throughout the research process to protect participants' privacy, and only essential information was collected, excluding unnecessary demographic details. No conflict of interest existed during the execution of this study. The researchers strictly followed anti-plagiarism policies, ensuring that all sources were properly cited and that the study was free from any form of plagiarism. Finally, the results were interpreted without bias, guaranteeing objectivity and integrity.

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